

New Urban Women Identity Construction and Rural Patriarchy Deconstruction: An Ethnographic Discourse Analysis of Duànqīn

Qi Yi¹

Abstract

This study delves into the phenomenon of duànqīn (kinship disconnection) among new urban women in China, exploring the social-psychological mechanisms that drive this trend. Through an ethnographic discourse analysis of 89 posts on the social media platform Xiaohongshu, the research uncovers the linguistic representations and social mechanisms that underlie the resistance to traditional gender roles and rural patriarchy. The study employs a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative analyses, to identify the core subject of this discourse as educated, mobile women who are challenging the cultural expectations imposed on them. The findings indicate that these women, experiencing kinship burnout, are actively deconstructing rural patriarchy by rejecting the traditional roles that confine them to submission and economic support within their families of origin. Instead, they are constructing new identities that emphasize self-motivation, independence, and gender equality. This empowerment is leading to a redefinition of family relationships and a pursuit of more harmonious and equal intimate connections. The research contributes to the understanding of the evolving dynamics of gender roles and kinship in the context of China’s rapid urbanization and social change. It offers insights into the challenges faced by women navigating the complexities of social mobility and the reconstruction of their identities within the rural-urban continuum.

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Keywords

ethnographic discourse analysis, China, new urban women, social mobility, patriarchy deconstruction

¹ School of Foreign Studies, University of Science and Technology Beijing,
E-mail: m202211169@xs.ustb.edu.cn

Introduction

During the 2024 Chinese Spring Festival, a time when family gatherings are of utmost importance, Chinese social media platforms like Xiaohongshu (the Chinese counterpart of Facebook) and Weibo (the Chinese counterpart of Twitter) witnessed a heated discussion on the topic of *duànqīn*, which means kinship disconnection literally. By the fourth day of the Spring Festival, the hashtag-led topic ‘Relatives separation as a family unit quietly occurs in rural areas’ had become a hot search on Weibo, garnering over 100 million views (CCTV News, 2024). Therefore, *duànqīn* phenomenon as a social media practice has turned into a discourse practice, inspiring researchers digging into its mechanism.

In existing studies, Chen Youhua and Zong Hao (2023) explored the kinship disconnection as a result of modernization, where young people rationally choose their relationships, reflecting the structural reshaping of social networks. Another study focuses on the phenomenon of kinship break-off and associates it with the individualization of contemporary youth within the broader social context of modernization (Yu, 2024). Scholars argue that Chinese social modernization inevitably leads to the reconstruction of family patterns, where individuals, especially the young, distance themselves from their kinship ties to actively engage in the society of such a China-typical modernization. Nevertheless, researchers have yet to conduct detailed investigations or provide comprehensive explanations. Certain aspects of this topic still require clarification. Firstly, the term “*qīn*” which refers to relatives or kinship necessitates further elucidation to better understand its implications within the context of kinship break-off. Secondly, it is crucial to investigate the identities of the voices participating in this discourse and their motivations for sharing their experiences. The existing studies have yet to address the discourse subject in a comprehensive manner, often referring to them collectively as ‘youth.’ Therefore, the subjectivity of this phenomenon calls for a deeper exploration.

To address these gaps, empirical discourse analysis is applied to delve into the original textual materials collected from social media platforms. Through a bottom-up ethnographic discourse analysis, it explored the real discourse subject and the social psychological mechanism of this evolution by examining the linguistic representations of *duànqīn* discourse. In particular, through quantitative and qualitative mixed method, the author discovered that women, particularly within the emerging urban demographic, constitute the subject of discourse.

1. Kinship Transformation in Modernized China

Kinship has been a core theme in anthropology, with the most attractive research, according to Mary Douglas (2003), being to understand the concept of patriarchy. Marshall Sullins (2013) proposing kinship as constructed through shared living conditions and shared memories. In the context of modern social mobility, kinship has continued to play a significant role in China, especially in rural areas, where the concept of *chāxùgélǚ* (pattern of difference sequence) has been central to understanding relationships between Chinese people (Zhou, 2022). However, the emergence of *duànqīn* phenomenon appears

to violate this philosophical underpinning, sparking heated discussion as it suggests a shift in the traditional understanding of kinship amid China’s broader social and economic transformations. Therefore, the study of this duànqīn discourse offers an opportunity to explore the deconstruction of rural patriarchy in the face of social changes, providing insights into the evolving dynamics of gender roles, women identity evolution under the impact of urbanization.

Modernization and industrialism are recognized as factors that accelerate social mobility (Cheng, 1995). In the context of a rapidly urbanizing economy, particularly after the Reform and opening-up policy in 1978, lower social classes have greater opportunities for education and career mobility (Chen and Qin, 2014; Yang et al., 2016). The China Development Research Foundation (2019) emphasizes that enhancing intergenerational mobility among Chinese residents is crucial for realizing the Chinese Dream, but it also widens the urban-rural and intergenerational gaps. The impact of social mobility on kinship ties and attitudes towards intimate relationships has been extensively studied (Friedman, 2014; Chan, 2018). Studies in China have explored intergenerational cultural dissonance and parent-child conflict in relation to mobility (Choi, He and Harachi, 2008). However, it is premature to conclude that upward mobility is universally negative (Chan, 2018). It is necessary to reexamine how mobility affects kinship, particularly why females express a desire to disconnect the kinship. This paper investigates how the values gap resulting from social mobility leads to a shift in kinship by examining the failure of family-of-origin to provide emotional support.

Kinship is not limited to biological relations but is also a cultural metaphor representing intrinsic connections and intersubjective belonging (Sahlins, 2013). In rural China, kinship is characterized by strong collectivism, and individuals from families registered as agricultural households are considered part of rural families (Yang, 2019). Disadvantaged socioeconomic status tends to be passed down from parents to children in rural families, despite observed intergenerational career mobility in both urban and rural settings (Yang, 2019). Social relationship networks, including familial kinship and social mobility, mutually interact (Liu, 2019). Scholars have examined the impact of social mobility on kinship relationships. On one hand, successful families who migrated from rural to urban areas for business tend to maintain close contact with their birth relatives, preserving traditional rural customs (Liu, 2019). On the other hand, individuals who experience upward mobility through education and career advancement in metropolitan cities distance themselves from their birth families. This disconnection from family of origin, kinship, and social class, driven by a desire for personal autonomy, is referred to as individualization (Beck and Beck-Gernsheim, 2001).

In the Chinese context, disconnection represents a departure from familiar society (Hou and Li, 2020). Some scholars argue that it is the exhaustion or lack of support within kinship networks, rather than the social capital functions of kinship, that affects people’s ties to their families (Han, 2023). Many studies regard duànqīn (breaking up kinship) as an inevitable consequence of modernization, social mobility, and individualization (Chen and Zong, 2023; Yu, 2024). Tang (2024) argues that quanqin (maintaining kinship) reflects the choice of youth to no longer engage with old kinship networks, as they fail to rebuild their own social networks in modern lives and careers. Scholars found that the post-

1990s generation and Gen Z are increasingly detached from their relatives (Hu and Han, 2022). Some further suggest that this detachment is not solely due to a lack of interest in family relationships but is influenced by complex changes in social structure and lifestyle. However, existing research primarily focuses on interpersonal pattern changes related to social mobility and may overlook the group characteristics and empirical examination of discourse practices. How women act in rural patriarchy under social mobile perspective remains under-researched.

2. Rural Patriarchy Deconstruction in Modernized China

Empowered women are the mainstream of rural patriarchy deconstruction. However, deconstruction represents not just a detraditionalization, but also at the same time a process of reconstructing tradition (Jin, 2011). Traditional patriarchy in China is featured as traditional gender role, which emphasis on the female submission and male power. With the modernization progressing, traditional patriarchy is deconstructed.

In 2020, the number of female employees in urban units reached 67.794 million, marking a significant increase of 19.179 million compared to 2010, representing a growth rate of 39.5% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). The status and image of women in China have improved under the influence of the market economy. Highly educated single women in Beijing embody characteristics such as self-motivation, independence, and a departure from traditional norms (Hou and Li, 2020). Meanwhile, Lin et al. (2022) discovered that migrants in urban China face challenges in attaining urban identities under acculturation theories.

While these articles provide a comprehensive analysis of professional aspirations, living conditions, marital perspectives, and pragmatism in urban cities, there is still a gap in understanding the evolution of intimate relationships within this demographic. The exploration of how intimate relationships are influenced by, or influence, the journey towards self-realization and future social evolution remains an under-researched area. The changing living patterns, social capital, and emotional needs in contemporary China have influenced how young people perceive and interact with their relatives (Hu and Han, 2022). Rather than lacking interest in relationships, they seek equal and harmonious intimate relationships that empower them in the Byung-Chul Han's (2015) *burnout society*.

In a word, the ethnography approach to discourse analysis can reveal the community and identity construction of particular groups by analyzing their language usage. In new media, virtual ethnography observes the discourse phenomena and collects data and then analyses them by textual coding and then theoretical construction. Thus, *duànqīn* discourse represents individuals' self-reports on the exhaustion and disappointment they experience in family relationships, leading to a rejection of the emotional labor that is undervalued and expected of them. As an anti-disciplinary feminist perspective, it signifies the rejection of rural patriarchal traditions in China by those who have achieved social mobility through their own efforts. It reflects the empowerment and establishment of independent identities among new urban women. In this paper, which aims to provide

fresh insights into contemporary feminist discourse studies, the following questions will be explored through an ethnographic lens within the social discourse:

- a. What are the features of subject and linguistic representations of duànqīn discourse?
- b. What is the social psychological mechanism of duànqīn discourse?

3. Methodology

This study employs ethnographic approaches to discourse. It aims to analyze discourse representations, identify subject characteristics, and uncover the underlying social psychological mechanisms. The mixed-method combines quantitative and qualitative analyses to form a comprehensive approach. The quantitative aspect utilizes an online tool called Weiciyun, accessible at <https://www.weiciyun.com/>, which supports word segmentation, frequency statistics, and analysis, enabling the identification of core vocabularies and the extraction of thematic content from the text.

3.1. Ethnographic Discourse Analysis

Ethnography has its origins in the field of anthropology, particularly in the works of scholars like Malinowski and Boas. It concerns how humans act and make meaning with the knowledge of language (Hymes, 1964). This study is based on an ethnographic investigation conducted from March to May 2024, adopting a virtual ethnography approach proposed by Hine (2000) to collect data from the social media platforms Xiaohongshu and Weibo.

While ethnography provides detailed, methodologically and epistemologically grounded descriptions, it is often narrowly and mistakenly viewed as merely a descriptive account of experiences. To address this shortcoming, ethnographic discourse analysis connects various levels of discourse and context, and employs specific methodological strategies to capture the dynamic ethnographic and sociopolitical contexts within which language is situated and to which it contributes and responds.

In the field of linguistics, ethnography conceives of society as “non-homogeneous, composed of a variety of features,” with “part–whole relationships” being central to the analytical work (Bloomaert and Dong, 2010). This approach focuses on interpreting the multiple systems and interrelationships within the societal structure, from a perspective of complexity, diversity, and interrelatedness. In the domain of linguistics, ethnography explores the multifaceted interaction of language ideologies (Wang and Li, 2024), which are shaped by society, community, group, and culture (Bloomaert and Dong, 2010). In essence, the ethnographic approach to linguistics perceives language as a social behavior of human beings, and studying language is a means to unpack social systems.

As a theoretical perspective, ethnographic discourse analysis claims that discourse should identify and highlight non-hegemonic narrative representations. By employing this

approach, this paper offers a semi-participant observation in the virtual field, situating the participants within the broader societal context of discourse.

3.2. Data Collection

This paper examines the language phenomena observed among netizens on Xiaohongshu, one of the most influential lifestyle and social commerce platforms. Xiaohongshu is a widely used social media platform in China (Chen and Gong, 2023). As of 2020, Xiaohongshu had 450 million registered users (Xin, 2024). This integrated social app offers multiple functions, allowing users to post multimodal content such as images, text, and videos (Wang et al., 2022). It is well-known as a product review community (Ren, 2018). The author's active engagement with users on Xiaohongshu enables them to conduct follow-up reviews that enhance the analysis of the content. As a regular user of Xiaohongshu, the author closely observes and reflects on the platform. The widespread use of Xiaohongshu provides a rich source of naturally occurring language materials for discourse analysis.

This article uses a quasi-manual data collector called Octopus which is excellent in web scraping based on python (Almaqbal, et al., 2019). We conducted Octopus collector to obtain people's opinions and thoughts on *duànqīn*, including the full texts, the first five comments including the replies from the posters per post on Xiaohongshu web version under hashtagged *duànqīn* topic. Up to 25 March 2024, 89 posts were detected and collected within which 12 news reports about *duànqīn* were manually filtered because they are not considered as self-reports. Finally, 38005 words in total construct the textual corpora and were coded under grounded theory by MAXQDA application. The author made sure that there are no privacy-sensitive contents in the collected samples such as personal name and family location. And if used as examples in this article the poster would be asked for permission.

3.3. Data Analysis

3.3.1. Quantitative analysis

Topic analysis was conducted with the assistance of the software Weiciyun which adopts the LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) algorithm (Wang et al., 2024). Weiciyun allows us to investigate the discourse representations by word frequency analysis according to various word categories and semantic network analysis which generates a word cloud for preliminary analysis (McNaught and Lam, 2010). By doing so we are able to discover the key word distribution of the original texts (see Table 1). It needs to pay attention that it is a complementary part of the whole interpretation of the qualitative analysis results followed. Due to the word cloud was made by Chinese, the results were translated into English in the form of chart.

3.3.2. Qualitative analysis

Based on the grounded theory, data were analyzed using Strauss and Corbin's (2008) mode of analysis, through constant comparative method, applying levels of open, axial, and selective coding with MAXQDA software. Grounded theory coding is a qualitative

method aiming to generate novel theory based on empirical experience materials (Strauss, 1987). Without theoretical presumption, the researchers should directly observe their raw data. This article employs grounded theory to conduct textual analysis, utilizing MAXQDA for coding and assisted by Weiciyun for frequency statistics of theme words. Firstly, open coding is conducted on the 62 texts, followed by axial coding to construct specific categories. Thirdly, selective coding is used to establish themes. Finally, 15 texts were used in theoretical saturation test. The coding process took two rounds: they were first coded by the author, and then coded by another assistant to ensure the reliability and validity of the coding.

3.4. Theoretical Saturation Test

To test whether the concepts, categories, and theories proposed in this article have reached theoretical saturation, this study employed theoretical sampling and encoded the remaining 15 textual data. No new concepts, categories, or theoretical relationships were discovered, indicating that theoretical saturation has been achieved.

3.5. Ethnic Consideration

Virtual ethnography adheres to fieldwork ethics including non-defamation, anonymity, confidentiality and consent (Carter, 2005, as cited in Piao, 2012). The data collected from the social media Xiaohongshu with a consent from the bloggers. To ensure ethical considerations and protect user privacy, informed consent was obtained from the bloggers and content bloggers, the author asked for their permission of using their contents including the title, text and comments, while their user name and related information are protected. The consent process involved clearly explaining the research objectives, the nature of data collection, and the assurance of anonymity and confidentiality. They were given the option to withdraw their consent at any time during the study.

4. Quantitative Findings: Discourse Representations

4.1. Who is the subject?

As in Table 1, the top 23 words constitute the theme of duànqīn data. The terms “young people”, “back home”, “small family”, “rural areas”, “spring festival” demonstrate that the discourse originates from the scene when women go back rural home from urban cities in the spring festival. The study of context is a matter for ethnography (Bloommaert and Dong, 2010). Duànqīn as a hot discussion topic emerged in the spring festival of 2024, occurred with a background of family gathering where young adults in their 30th went back countryside from big cities to be with their parents and relatives. They cannot get along well with their parents and other rural relatives such as uncles and cousins and so on.

Table 1. Word frequency of duànqīn data

Word	Frequency	TF-IDF
Young people	27	0.034822501
Increasingly	12	0.019503322
Don't know	11	0.017070074
Xiaohongshu	9	0.018992899
Close relationship	8	0.013341788
Have or not	8	0.013341788
Parent-child relationship	8	0.013341788
Uncomfortable	6	0.010613824
Look down on	6	0.012661932
Chaoshan people	6	0.012661932
Go back to one's hometown	6	0.010613824
Psychology	6	0.010986441
Generation	6	0.011966541
Don't like	6	0.011427153
Never	5	0.009155367
Family education	5	0.009522627
Depression	5	0.009522627
Not easy	5	0.009155367
Normal	5	0.009522627
Ungrateful child	5	0.009155367
Irresponsible	4	0.009094688
Whether or not	4	0.007618102
Lifestyle	4	0.007618102
Personal growth	4	0.007618102

Note. TF-IDF = term frequency-inverse document frequency.

4.2. What does qin refer to?

83% of the users of Xiaohongshu are between 18 and 34 years old (Dragon Social, 2019). The semantic network distribution (see Figure 1) has demonstrated that in the semantic field of the discourse duànqīn, the term “qin” refers to a relationship circle network centered around the core node of “parents”, and surrounded by five outer nodes forming the first layer, including the vocabulary terms “family,” “origin,” “children,” “relatives,” and “relationships”. While the terms “mother,” “mom,” “father,” “emotion,” “society,”

depict subjective emotional burnout and trauma from the family kinship. Phrases like “pass on the family by giving birth to a son,” “taking it for granted” and “wipe the slate clean” syntagmatically reveal these women’s overwhelming struggles from traditional values in rural culture.

Some researches claim that the kinship disconnection happens when the family of origin fails to provide social capital for the second generation (Hu and Han, 2022). While from the textual mining, we found that the lack of “love” takes significant role in the kinship disconnection. And therefore, *duànqīn* is the representation of their disappointment in the kinship relationship expectation, the retrospective result of being “moral kidnapped” by the Important Others, the awakening after trying to getting rid of the internal friction. This kind of kinship burnout roots in the structural tension under the gap between urban and rural order. Therefore, kinship as emotional value for the young adult women is more explanatory than as their social capital resource and social support. These group, say, new urban women, learned and worked in urban cities, raising awareness and feeling empowered (Baylina and Rodó-Zárate, 2020). They care for their mental well-being (Chan, 2018), in which sense it does not fall into the category of initialization but rather, it is the frustration of trying to get involved into the intimate kinship experience that drives them to this disconnection in the course of social connection. it echoes the dissociative hypothesis by Sorokin (1959). New urban women act in the social transformation because of their feminist identity, which is key in rural change and women empowerment (Baylina and Rodó-Zárate, 2020). Young women are active agents of social transformation thanks to their feminist activism, a key factor for rural change and young women’s empowerment.

5. Qualitative Findings: Social-psychological Mechanism

Traditional patriarchy has relied on kinship and local ties while the population movement has made a shift (Jin, 2011). In other words, the mobility causes changes in family structure and kinship model, which represents a deconstruction of traditional rural systems. While mobile peasant families who go-up to cities to do business and “wu-gong” (务工), say, casual labor or gig work, keep intimate connections with families in countryside, the new urban class who realized upwards mobility through tertiary education, obtaining job opportunity and get marriage away from home, tend to distance themselves with the family-of-origin. Among them, female stand out as a mainstream of deconstructing the familial patriarchy. By coding the *duànqīn* data (see Table 2), we empirically found women deconstruct rural patriarchy by resisting against traditional gender role, battling with poverty culture and perceiving kinship burnout from family-of-origin.

Table 2. Coding duànqīn data

Open coding	Axial coding	Selective coding
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I was asked to give birth. 2. I was asked to marry. 3. I was asked to be subject. 4. I was asked to support economically male siblings. 5. My parents are overwhelming. 6. They were absent in my childhood. 7. They live a whole life in rural places and their era was past. 8. I am regarded odd when I go back home. 9. All they bring to me are negative emotions. 10. I suffered emotional “black hole” when staying with them. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resistance against traditional gender role. 2. Battle with poverty culture. 3. Perception kinship burnout from family-of-origin. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Construction of new urban women identity 2. Deconstruction of rural patriarchy

5.1. Resistance against Traditional Gender Role

Stark’s (1991) empirical survey of 806 undergraduates show that those who believe strongly in traditional roles reported low levels of intimacy. It suggests that traditional gender roles which assumed duties for men and women face challenges over time especially in the contemporary society. Traditional roles concepts historically and typically expected women to be nurturing and submissive to their husband, with an emphasis on maintaining a supportive and caring role within the family, and even supposed to give up their career and professional opportunities. In contemporary era, traditional kinship was deconstructed in terms of its patriarchy.

Example (1)

“...But in the countryside, I was a selfish old woman who was neither married nor had children, couldn’t make jokes, had a weird temper, had mental problems, and was unwilling to use money to support my uncle’s family and my cousins’ family...” (*Blogger 2, Position 3*) [ST:而在农村，我是一个没结婚没生娃开不起玩笑的脾气古怪脑子有问题的不愿拿钱供养我舅舅一家和表弟们几家的自私老女人..... (博主2, 位置3)]

Example (2)

“...They always say that I have hardened my wings because of my work, that I am rebellious, ungrateful, inconsiderate and disrespectful of my parents. Do I have to lick them like a dog to make them happy?...” (*Blogger 14, Position 2*) [ST:动不动就说我工作了，翅膀硬了，反骨叛逆，不懂得感恩，不体谅父母，不尊重父母，难道我要像狗一样舔他们，他们才会开心吗..... (博主14, 位置2)]

Women resist the traditional women roles such as the expectations to marry, have children, and be submissive daughters, by challenging the norms associated with these roles. This resistance can be observed in the excerpts from *duànqīn* where, in Example (1), the blogger felt frustrated about being perceived negatively in the countryside, judged for being an unmarried woman without children and are blamed by her temperament and her unwillingness to support financially her uncle’s (father’s brother) and cousin’s families. The ironic tone of self-depreciation reveals their pressure to conform to societal norms and expectation in countryside. While in Example (2), the blogger showed her feelings of being accused of becoming rebellious, ungrateful, and inconsiderate due to their focus on work, which leads them to prioritize their individual pursuits over family obligations. By voicing these, the blogger reveals her resistance against the submissive persona traditionally assigned to women in rural cultures. A survey demonstrated women who had a greater internalization of gender roles, say, femininity, reported higher fear of negative evaluation compared with men (Villanueva-Moya and Expósito, 2023). While both the two examples showed how they complained the negative evaluation received at home in the countryside, it in turn how they took the step to resist it by expressing and acting. And that is how women empowerment is defined.

5.2, “Battle” against Poverty Culture

Women born from countryside then moved to urban cities via education and career feel the disconnection and, in fact, choose to disconnect with their family or relatives because the rural places feature traditional patriarchy norms centered around marriage, childbearing, and subservience to the family’s needs, and rural families do not receive lots of education thus they do not and would not understand their daughters who gained individual values, empowered by economic independence and exposed to in some degree feminism perspectives. The poverty rural culture takes it for granted asking money from financial-independent relatives. However, women such as the cited bloggers also earn themselves with many efforts in big cities. That is why they feel the rural relatives are bottomless pit in terms of borrowing money without giving back. The expert in Example (3) which said “the poor choose to disconnect their relatives to show their independence” implies those women who voiced *duànqīn* usually have a rural family background.

Example (3)

...The rich and aristocrats are marrying each other to expand the power and scope of their families, while the poor choose to disconnect their relatives to show their independence... (*Blogger 4, Position 19*) [ST:富人贵族都在联姻扩大家族势力和范围，穷人选择断亲展示独立..... (博主4, 位置19)]

Example (4)

...Be sure to stay away from relatives who are not in a good financial position. Because in addition to bringing you internal friction, traps, and digging holes, they will not even give you gratitude and thanks... (*Blogger 39, Position 1-2*) [ST:一定要远离财务状况不好的亲戚。因为他们除了给你带来内耗, 陷阱, 挖坑, 连感恩和感谢都不会给你..... (博主39, 位置1-2)]

The concept of the culture of poverty encompasses not only the economic aspects but also the cognitive impact of impoverishment. Groups facing economic challenges often experience heightened levels of stress and adversity in their struggle for survival. The culture of poverty theory, initially proposed by American anthropologist Oscar Lewis in 1959 based on his study of five Mexican families, delineates a way of life that is transmitted intergenerationally within impoverished families and communities. As a distinct subculture characterized by its unique values, attitudes, and behaviors, it perpetuates the cycle of poverty by establishing particular norms and beliefs (Li, 2018). In rural areas of China, these norms and values, such as “More children, more blessings” (多子多福) and “favoring sons over daughters” (重男轻女), emerge within a specific historical, political, and economic context, as groups adopt these values and corresponding behaviors as a means of survival. However, due to a lack of ideological awareness, these groups remain trapped in poverty due to structural constraints (Li, 2018). It results in intergenerational conflict in terms of cultural dissonance under modernized society rather than the decline of kinship bonds rooted in China.

5.3. Kinship Burnout from Family-of-origin

Kinship support is usually characterized as physical and psychological support, say, financial and mental support. Han Ruixia (2023) tested the hypothesis that kinship support is negatively associated with young people’s tendency to disconnect. From a functionalism perspective, the family serves as a crucial repository of social capital for its members (Chen and Zong, 2023). Similarly, from a socioeconomic status perspective, the social status of a family including parents’ educational level, family income and parents career play a significant role in parent-child relationship (Zhu, et al., 2015). This perspective often emphasizes the economic benefits that a family can provide to its younger members, such as financial support for education or career development. They both underscore the economic support for a child or adolescence.

Example (5)

...Home has no warmth in my heart. It is like a huge emotional black hole, which can easily turn me, who is emotionally stable, cheerful, confident, lively and interesting, into that lunatic. (*Blogger 2, Position 2*) [ST:家在我心里是没有温度的, 它像一个巨大的情绪黑洞, 轻而易举把情绪稳定、开朗自信、活泼有趣的我变成那个疯子。(博主2, 位置2)]

Example (6)

...My parents were not chosen by me. Their arrogance and indifference made me suffer throughout my adolescence. They tried to kidnap me morally until I finally became financially independent. Why should I be considerate and “filial” to such people? (*Blogger*

5, *Position 3*) [ST:不是我自己选择的父母，用自大和冷漠让我痛苦了整个青春期，直到好不容易经济独立还想试图道德绑架我。为什么我要体谅和“孝顺”这样的人？ (博主5, 位置3)]

However, this economic-centric view may not fully account for the experiences of adults who choose to distance themselves from their families of origin, particularly in rural settings. The data presented in this paper suggest that adults who feel emotionally neglected or hurt by their families—perceiving a lack of warmth akin to an “emotional black hole” as in Example (5)—often cite a failure in communication as a key factor. They struggle to convey their divergent values and aspirations to their parents. But they failed. The spiritual function of a family is vital for adults who have migrated to urban areas for education, employment, or other reasons. The virtual ethnography indicates that these women are part of a new urban demographic. They are characterized by their self-reliance and economic independence, embracing modern values and forging new identities. This shift can lead to kinship burnout, represented by “kidnap morally”, “suffer” as in Example (6), a result of the tension between their urban lifestyles and the traditional expectations rooted in their rural family backgrounds.

6. Discussion

6.1. Social Mobility and Kinship Dynamics

Sahlins (2013, p. 28) defined kinship as mutuality of being. In other words, the kinship is constructive. Even when relationships are severed, the underlying family tie remains unchanged. On the contrary, the family conflict represented in *Duànqīn* discourse itself implies a hope for mutual-understanding and reconciliation. It is the intergenerational gaps in values or norms influences family communication patterns. This survey found that, in the contemporary era, the intergenerational conflict among Chinese rural women lies in cultural dissonance, as noted by Choi, He, and Harachi (2008). The ways in which the younger generation identifies themselves has changed. Specifically, it is no longer possible for new urban women to be expected to be submissive daughters at home (Shen, 2016). Self-motivated behaviors such as receiving high education and getting a job in metropolitan areas have empowered them a new identity where women are able to be individual or self-dependent, no longer submissive to parents' authority within the rural family and gender ideology.

Social mobility is an inevitable byproduct of modernization, and difficulties in connecting with families-of-origin and a sense of distance from one's 'roots' are cost of upward mobility (Curl, 2013). Nevertheless, this does not necessarily lead to a radical variation in terms of kinship ties and the significance of family values in Chinese society. Although existing articles point out the social background of *duànqīn* phenomena, this paper is one of the first to point out it is women and scientifically new urban women who are suffering from this dynamic.

6.2. New Urban Women Identities and Rural Patriarchy Deconstruction

Represented as “Duànqīn”, women have demonstrated their liberation from the oppression of traditional gender roles and social labor where they had been previously restrained in the family. This empowerment enables women to construct an independent and equal identity, which encompasses self-dependence, the pursuit of self-realization, awareness of gender equality, an expectation of better intimate relationships, and a redefinition of family and subjectivity.

This rise of individualistic values has empowered this young generation, granting them greater agency in shaping their identities (Koo and Zhan, 2023). On the other hand, it reflects that new urban women are the main force of rural patriarchy deconstruction, which requires and forces a woman to be submissive to traditional roles.

This paper is one of the first to employ an ethnographic discourse analysis approach to dig out the subject of the discourse by analyzing the linguistic representation.

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the social-psychological mechanisms underlying the phenomenon of duànqīn from a sociolinguistic perspective. Specifically, it delved into the subject characteristics, discourse representations, and social practices associated with the continuous kinship-changing dynamics observed in China.

The findings reveal that the subject of the duànqīn discourse is primarily composed of adult women born into rural families, who have accessed educational opportunities and achieved social mobility, and experience a sense of burnout from their family, where their parents mainly tend to pressure them to marry and have children and educate them from a rural culture and value system.

This study’s exploration of the duànqīn phenomenon from a new perspective, employing a novel methodological approach, contributes to the broader understanding of female identity construction and the deconstruction of patriarchal structures within the rural-urban mobility framework. By shedding light on the nuanced social-psychological mechanisms underlying this complex issue, the findings have important implications for addressing the challenges faced by socially mobile women navigating the evolving kinship dynamics in contemporary China.

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